

The 4th
**INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
ON THE PHYSICS OF OPTICAL
MATERIALS AND DEVICES**

ICOM 2015

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

The 4TH International Conference on the Physics of Optical Materials and Devices

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Editors: Dr. Miroslav Dramićanin

Dr. Bruno Viana

Dr. Rachid Mahiou

Published and printed by: Institut za nuklearne nauke "Vinča" Beograd

Print run: 300

ISBN: 978-86-7306-134-4

August 2015, Budva, Montenegro

CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

538.9(048)(0.034.2)

INTERNATIONAL Conference on Physics of Optical Materials and Devices (4 ; 2015 ; Budva)

Book of Abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / The 4th International Conference on the Physics of Optical Materials and Devices - ICOM 2015, Budva, Montenegro, August 31st - September 4th, 2015 ; [editors Miroslav Dramićanin, Bruno Viana, Rachid Mahiou]. - Beograd : Institut za nuklearne nauke "Vinča", 2015 (Beograd : Institut za nuklearne nauke "Vinča"). - 1 USB fleš memorija ; 1 x 3 x 6 cm

Sistemski zahtevi: Nisu navedeni. - Nasl. sa naslovne strane dokumenta. - Tiraž 300. - Bibliografija uz većinu apstrakata.

ISBN 978-86-7306-134-4

а) Физика кондензоване материје - Апстракти б) Физика чврстог стања - Апстракти
COBISS.SR-ID 216811788

ICOM 2015

**The 4TH International Conference on the Physics of
Optical Materials and Devices**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Budva, Montenegro

August 31st – September 4th, 2015

Scientific advisory committee

- G. Boulon (France)
- O. Malta (Brasil)
- P. Dorenbos (The Netherlands)
- M. Popova (Russia)
- J. Holsa (Finland)
- M. Brik (Estonia)
- M. Bettinelli (Italy)
- L. Carlos (Portugal)
- Ph. Boutinaud (France)
- S. Jobic (France)
- B. Moine (France)
- J. Nedeljković (Serbia)
- J. Capobianco (Canada)
- S. Fujihara (Japan)
- S. Tanabe (Japan)
- M. Peng (China)
- W. Strek (Poland)
- A. Djurišić (China)
- D. Jaque Garzía (Spain)
- Ph. Goldner (France)
- A. Ferrier (France)
- T.M. Chen (Taiwan)
- P.Deren (Poland)
- A. Meijerink (The Netherlands)
- L.Bausa (Spain)
- J.L.Adam (France)
- M. Ferrari (Italy)
- C. V. Santilli (Brasil)
- W. Ka-Leung (Hong Kong)
- M. Marinović-Cincović (Serbia)
- M. Ferrari (Italy)

Organizing and Program committee

- M. Dramićanin (Serbia)
- Ž. Antić (Serbia)
- K. Vuković (Serbia)
- M. Sekulić (Serbia)
- M. Antonov (Serbia)
- R. Krsmanović (Serbia)
- V. Đorđević (Serbia)
- D. Jovanović (Serbia)
- B. Milićević (Serbia)
- M. Medić (Serbia)
- S. Čulubrk (Serbia)
- T. Gavrilović (Serbia)
- B. Viana (France)
- Ph. Goldner (France)
- Ph. Boutinaud (France)
- R. Mahiou (France)
- G. Chadeyron (France)
- M. Ferrari (Italy)

INFLUENCE OF RESTORATIVE PROCEDURES ON ENDODONTICALLY TREATED PREMOLARS: FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF A CT-SCAN BASED MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Tatjana Maravić^a, Darko Vasiljević^b, Ivana Kantardžić^a, Tijana Lainović^a, Ognjan Lužanin^c
and Larisa Blažić^d

^a*Faculty of Medicine, School of Dentistry, University of Novi Sad, 3 Hajduk Veljkova, Novi Sad, Serbia, vukadinov.tatjana@gmail.com, ivanakantardzic@gmail.com, tijana.lainovic@gmail.com*

^b*Institute of Physics, University of Belgrade, 118 Pregrevica, Belgrade, Serbia, darko@ipb.ac.rs*

^c*Faculty of Technical Sciences, Department of Production Engineering, University of Novi Sad, 6 Trg Dositeja Obradovića, Novi Sad, Serbia, luzanin@uns.ac.rs*

^d*Faculty of Medicine, School of Dentistry, Clinic of Dentistry of Vojvodina, University of Novi Sad, 12 Hajduk Veljkova, Novi Sad, Serbia, larisa.blazic@gmail.com*

In every-day dental practice, an endodontically treated tooth with mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity is usually restored with composite resin. The restorations of these biomechanically weakened teeth are often of limited durability [1]. Thus, additional procedures, such as the inclusion of palatal and buccal cusp into the cavity (MODP, MODPB), and/or fiber-reinforced composite (FRC) posts, are used in an attempt to improve the prognosis of the tooth and the restoration [2,3]. The aim of this study was to determine whether these procedures are beneficial, or the removal of healthy dental tissues during these procedures has a negative effect. Finite element analysis (FEA) has emerged in recent decades as a valid method of research in biomedical sciences due to ethical issues and complexity of factors that influence “in vivo” experimental studies.

In order to make a highly accurate three-dimensional tooth model, a precise medical imaging technique (Computerized Tomography-CT) was used in this study. Based on CT scans of an extracted maxillary second premolar, six tooth models (MOD, MODP, MODPB, MOD+FRC, MODP+FRC, MODPB+FRC) were created in SolidWorks 2014 software (Dassault Systemes SolidWorks Corp, USA). Each model was subjected to a summary force of 150 N on the occlusal surface simulating the natural biting pattern and maximal von Mises stresses were calculated using FEA.

In the presented study, the von Mises stresses in dental tissues (especially enamel), showed lower values in MODP and MODPB preparations, regardless of the use of FRC. MOD+FRC model showed lower stresses in the enamel compared to MOD, and FRC seems to have switched some of the stresses from dental tissues to the composite filling.

Acknowledgement

Supported by the Serbian Ministry of Education and Science, contract No. III45016 and TR035020.

[1] C.L. Lin, Y.H. Chang, P.R. Liu. *J. Dent.* 36 (2008) 194-203.

[2] K. Kainose, M. Nakajima, R. Foxton, N. Wakabayashi, J. Tagami. *Int. Endod. J.* (2014) doi:10.1111/iej.12397.

[3] I. Kantardzic, D. Vasiljevic, L. Blazic, O. Luzanin. *Croat. Med. J.* 53 (2012) 568-576.